

Uremic Pericarditis: When The Kidneys Break The Heart!

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Description

The above images represent rapid accumulation of pericardial fluid in the setting uremia. Figure A is a 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) with subtle downsloping ST elevation (Spodick's sign) suggestive of pericarditis. Two-dimensional transthoracic echocardiographic views in the parasternal long axis (Figure B) and apical 4-chamber (Figure C) planes reveal large pericardial effusion with respirophasic compression of the right ventricle (RV) in diastole indicative of cardiac tamponade. The respiratory variation of the tricuspid valve inflow velocities of greater than 40% shown in Figure D is also highly suggestive of cardiac tamponade. Pericardiocentesis and hemodialysis (HD) resulted in resolution of the cardiac tamponade and improvement in the hemodynamic status.

Discussion

Uremic pericarditis as a cause of cardiac tamponade has long been recognized as a serious and potentially fatal condition; which mandates prompt diagnosis and treatment [1]. Classic physical examination findings include Beck's Triad (jugular venous distention, hypotension, and muffled heart sounds) and pulsus paradoxus [2].

Uremic pericarditis is a rare and serious complication of end-stage renal disease [3]. Bloodstream toxins irritate the pericardial sac causing release of inflammatory mediators leading to serous or hemorrhagic effusions, tamponade or constrictive pericarditis [4].

Uremic pericarditis typically resolves with the initiation or intensification of dialysis [5], but refractory cases may require anti-inflammatory agents [6], and prompt pericardial drainage may be necessary when pericardial effusions lead to cardiac tamponade [7].

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References

1. Baldwin JJ, Edwards JE. Uremic pericarditis as a cause of cardiac tamponade. *Circulation*. 1976 May;53(5):896-901.
2. Sternbach G. Claude Beck: cardiac compression triads. *J Emerg Med*. 1988 Sep-Oct;6(5):417-9.
3. Sadjadi SA, Mashahdian A. Uremic pericarditis: a report of 30 cases and review of the literature. *Am J Case Rep*. 2015 Mar 22;16:169-73.
4. Rehman KA, Betancor J, Xu B, et al. Uremic pericarditis, pericardial effusion, and constrictive pericarditis in end-stage renal disease: Insights and pathophysiology. *Clin Cardiol*. 2017 Oct;40(10):839-846.
5. Kwasnik EM, Koster K, Lazarus JM, et al. Conservative management of uremic pericardial effusions. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 1978 Nov;76(5):629-32.
6. Badwan O, Skoza W, Braghieri L, et al. When should pharmacologic therapies be used for uremic pericarditis? *Cleve Clin J Med*. 2023 Sep 1;90(9):549-554.
7. Fox HE, Yee JM, Weaver JC Jr, et al. Pericardial drainage operations in the management of uremic pericardial effusion. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 1977 Apr;73(4):504-10.

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